

NOAA Estuary-of-the-Month
Seminar Series No. 14

Lake Erie Estuarine Systems: Issues, Resources, Status, and Management

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Lake Erie Estuarine Systems: Issues, Resources, Status, and Management

Proceedings of a Seminar
Held May 4, 1988
Washington, D.C.

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE
Robert A. Mosbacher, Secretary
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
William E. Evans, Under Secretary

NOAA Estuarine Programs Office
Virginia K. Tippie, Director

LAKE ERIE AND ITS ESTUARINE SYSTEMS

(Issues, Resources, Status, and Management)

an
**ESTUARY-OF-THE-MONTH
SEMINAR**

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**THE NOAA ESTUARINE PROGRAMS OFFICE
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edited
by
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PREFACE

This volume contains the proceedings of a one-day seminar on Lake Erie with emphasis on its nearshore and coastal wetland areas. The presentations were made on 4 May 1988 at the Herbert C. Hoover Building of the U.S. Department of Commerce in Washington, D.C., as part of a series of "Estuary-of-the-Month" seminars sponsored by the NOAA Estuarine Programs Office (EPO). The objectives of this series are to bring to public attention the important research and management issues regarding our nation's estuaries.

The Laurentian Great Lakes of North America represent our nation's "sweetwater seas" and its "fourth coast." The National Sea Grant College Program administered by NOAA includes active research, education and extension programs in most of the Great Lakes States. Furthermore, the southern shore of Lake Erie in Ohio is the site of the only freshwater National Estuarine Research Reserve. Therefore, it was appropriate that the Estuary-of-the-Month seminar series would include Lake Erie.

The present seminar was originally arranged and organized by Dr. C. E. "Eddie" Herdendorf, recent director of the Ohio Sea Grant Program as well as director of The Ohio State University's Center for Lake Erie Area Research (CLEAR) and its Franz Theodore Stone Laboratory on South Bass Island in Lake Erie. In view of his ensuing retirement, Dr. Herdendorf asked me to assume the roles of coordinator and moderator of the seminar and editor of the proceedings.

The title of this volume undoubtedly raises some eyebrows. Indeed, researchers actively debate the use of the terms "estuary" and "estuarine" to describe certain estuarine-like physical processes characteristic of many of Lake Erie's wetlands and its flooded tributary mouths. Contrasting views on the appropriate terminology are found in several of the presentations. Thus, it is important, in order to understand the estuarine-like characteristics of these areas, that these proceedings present first the geological and physical nature of Lake Erie and its coastal regions. The succeeding papers summarize the chemistry and biology of the nearshore and coastal areas, both within the historical context and the context of present conditions of pollution and physical modification. Of great importance to the future condition of the Lake Erie ecosystem are the views and policies of government, throughout the local, state or provincial, and national hierarchy as well as at the binational level. These issues are succinctly covered by representatives of the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's Great Lakes National Program Office, and Environment Canada's Inland Waters Directorate.

The seminar originated through discussions in 1987 between Dr. Herdendorf and Dr. James Thomas, then of the Estuarine Programs Office, followed by later coordination with Dr. Carl Berman and Dr. Joe Bishop of the EPO, as well as with Dr. Virginia Tippie, EPO Director. Special appreciation is extended to Ms. Terri Weininger for retyping several of the manuscripts, and to Ms. Nancy Creamer for editorial assistance, both at Heidelberg College. The Ohio Sea Grant College Program supported travel costs for two of the participants under federal grant number NA84AA-D-00079, the National Sea Grant College Program, NOAA, U.S. Department of Commerce. Dr. David B. Baker, Director of the Water Quality Laboratory at Heidelberg College, generously provided the use of computers, supplies, secretarial assistance, and some of my time for coordination and editorial efforts.

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CHEMICAL LIMNOLOGY AND CONTAMINANTS

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The chemical limnology of Lake Erie is a result of its morphometry and hydromechanics, and of the hydrological, topographical, geological, climatic and land-use characteristics of its watershed. Several of these characteristics have been presented already (Bedford, Herdendorf, Herdendorf and Krieger in this volume), but land-use and the contaminants derived from land activities need also to be noted because both have had a profound influence on the chemistry of Lake Erie since the advent of European settlement of the basin. This discussion will follow the route of the water from its precipitation onto the landscape, and its consequent movement with associated materials into the tributaries, on into the marshes and wetlands, and finally to the nearshore zone and open lake.

TRIBUTARIES

As previously discussed (Herdendorf), the natural characteristics of the Lake Erie basin vary greatly between the eastern and western ends of the lake. The southwestern and northern parts of the drainage are heavily agricultural, while a much greater proportion of the eastern two-thirds of the southern drainage is urbanized or forested. The nature of the soils also varies considerably. The combination of watershed sizes, soils, topography and land-use has influenced the kinds and amounts of various pollutants which enter the lake and affect its water and sediment chemistry.

Because of intensive row crop agriculture, the southwestern drainage contributes by far the greatest unit area losses of sediment and phosphorus, with average losses in some counties of 2.5 kg P per hectare per year (Internat. Joint Commission 1980). Because phosphorus, especially "bioavailable" phosphorus, has been shown to be the cause of much of the degradation of Lake Erie's water quality (Internat. Joint Commission 1980), a great deal of effort has been expended by both the U.S. and Canada to reduce the amount of phosphorus leaving the land and moving downstream to the lake. This effort is reflected in the 1983 Phosphorus Load Reduction Supplement to Annex 3 of the 1978 Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement between the two countries, and also in various reports on remedial programs (Honey Creek Joint Bd. Supervisors 1982, Great Lakes Phosphorus Task Force 1985, National Assoc. Conserv. Districts 1985).

Phosphorus arises from both point and nonpoint sources within the basin. While the amounts of phosphorus entering tributaries or the lake directly via point sources are computable from readily available data, attempts to quantify

the amount entering from nonpoint sources have been complicated by the large annual variability in climate. Fig. 1 shows the annual precipitation occurring in the Sandusky Basin (the second largest U.S. watershed tributary to Lake Erie excluding the Detroit River) from 1976 through 1985. Discharge in the Sandusky River (Fig. 1) is much more variable from year to year than precipitation because of the dependence of discharge on soil moisture conditions and the intensity and duration of individual storms. Total phosphorus, which includes that bound to sediment particles and organic matter in storm runoff as well as that dissolved in the water, is even more variable than discharge (Fig. 1).

Thus, efforts to evaluate the effectiveness of programs applied to land management practices, such as conservation tillage demonstration projects in the Lake Erie basin (e.g., Honey Creek Joint Bd. Supervisors 1982, Nat. Assoc. Conserv. Districts 1985), through measurement of the amount of reduction in the loading of phosphorus to the lake, must be carried out over many years in order to "average out" the large annual and seasonal variations (Richards 1987). Furthermore, the loadings measured near the mouth of a single tributary, such as the Sandusky River, cannot be extrapolated to other watersheds in the basin, such as the Maumee, the Huron or the Cuyahoga, because of largescale effects of watershed size, as well as differences in land-use, topography and soil types, on the transport of sediments and pollutants (Baker 1988). It is, therefore, difficult to predict quantitatively the reduction in phosphorus loadings, and the loadings of associated pollutants, which will result from the implementation of best management practices on the land. Nevertheless, because rural nonpoint sources contribute 51% (in 1980) of the total phosphorus loading to Lake Erie (Yaksich 1983), much emphasis has been placed on such programs over the past decade. (Urban nonpoint sources in 1980 supplied 6%, point sources 27%, and Lake Huron and the atmosphere 16% of the phosphorus load (Yaksich 1983)).

Another major source of phosphorus is treated sewage effluent. The 1972 Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement established a standard of 1.0 mg total P/L to be met by all municipal point sources discharging more than a million gallons (3,800 m³) of effluent per day (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985). Some of these point sources discharge into tributaries, while others discharge directly into Lake Erie along its shores or in its harbors. The Detroit plant is the single greatest source of phosphorus to Lake Erie via the Detroit River. The load from this facility has been reduced from 4,720 metric tons in 1975 to 789 metric tons in 1984. Table 1 shows the largest municipal wastewater treatment facilities discharging in the Lake Erie basin, their average annual flow rates and P concentrations, and their ranking among all Great Lakes Basin facilities. A target load of phosphorus to Lake Erie has been set at 11,000 metric tons per year (t/a). Because the load (estimated at 18,000 t/a in 1972) can only be reduced to 13,000 t/a if all municipal treatment plants discharge phosphorus at 1 mg/L, the remaining 2,000 t/a must be removed from the nonpoint sources (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985).

Figure 1. Annual variability and seasonal distribution of rainfall in northcentral Ohio and of discharge and loadings of total phosphorus, soluble reactive phosphorus, total suspended solids and nitrate+nitrite nitrogen in the Sandusky River at Fremont, Ohio (modified from Baker 1988).

Nitrate is another essential plant nutrient but not usually limiting to algal growth in Lake Erie. In fact, annual mean nitrate+nitrite concentrations have been increasing significantly over the last decade (Herdendorf 1984). Of more interest from the human health standpoint than from the standpoint of loading to Lake Erie, nitrate in drinking water supplies drawn from northwestern Ohio tributaries to the lake each spring exceeds the standard of 10 mg/L nitrate as N, above which nitrate has the potential to lead to methemoglobinemia in human infants as well as in some domestic animals (Ohio Coop. Ext. Serv. 1987). Nitrate in the Lake Erie watersheds derives from natural nitrogen fixation in the soil, water, and atmosphere, but also from faulty septic systems, urban sewage treatment effluent and from agricultural surface runoff and the effluent from drainage tiles, which are extensive beneath farm fields in the gently sloping, clayey soils of most of the southwestern drainage. The variability of its annual tributary loads is demonstrated in Fig. 1.

Agricultural herbicides used with corn and soybeans reach higher concentrations in rivers in northwestern Ohio than in rivers anywhere else in North America (Baker 1988). Their annual concentration pattern in streams is predictable: they always reach their highest concentrations in late spring or early summer in the first major storm runoff event following corn and soybean planting and then decline, at first rapidly, then more gradually to undetectable levels. Later storms usually give rise to brief increases in concentration (Baker et al. 1985). The height of the peak concentrations cannot be predicted, for herbicide concentrations, like those of phosphorus and sediment, are dependent largely on variable climatology. Atrazine, used with corn, and alachlor (Lasso™), used with corn and soybeans, both have reached peak

Table 1. Largest municipal wastewater treatment facilities in the Lake Erie Basin (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985).

Facility	1983 Average Flow Rate (10 ³ m ³ /d)	Annual Average P Concentration (mg/L)		Rank Among Great Lakes Facilities
		1983	1984	
Detroit, Michigan	2,646	0.79	0.85	1
Cleveland-Easterly, Ohio	502	0.69	0.33	4
Cleveland-Southerly, Ohio	349	0.69	0.80	7
Toledo, Ohio	315	1.30	1.09	9
Akron, Ohio	275	1.16	1.24	13
Erie, Pennsylvania	175	1.24	1.10	19
Fort Wayne, Indiana	135	0.83	0.69	25
Cleveland-Westerly, Ohio	133	1.52	1.15	26

concentrations near 100 µg/L (ppb) in some of the smaller tributaries to the lake (Baker et al. 1981, Baker 1988). Atrazine is known to be inhibitory to some native algae and vascular aquatic plants at the concentrations found in these watersheds; however, various studies have indicated that these effects are transitory and probably have no lasting effect on the composition or productivity of the aquatic plant communities (Krieger et al. 1988). Unlike atrazine, alachlor, which has a different mechanism of toxicity, apparently does not inhibit the productivity or alter the community structure of stream algae (Blake 1988). The toxic effects on algae and vascular aquatic plants of many of the other herbicides present together in storm runoff soon after planting are not known. Most insecticides are detectable for only brief periods if at all, at levels usually below 5 µg/L (Baker 1988), although slightly higher concentrations have on occasion been recorded in one western Lake Erie coastal marsh (Krieger, unpubl. data).

COASTAL WETLANDS

Most of the creeks and rivers debouching along the southwestern shore of Lake Erie possess "estuaries" (as defined by Brant and Herdendorf 1972), formed by a gradual rise in the lake level which drowned the lower tributary channels along with varying amounts of their floodplains. These riverine systems are also present along some other shores of the Great Lakes (e.g. Spain et al. 1969). The water in these wetlands is often a mixture of tributary and lake water and thus has an intermediate chemistry. Flow reversals are also frequent in at least the more lakeward portions of these systems. Hereafter in this report, these unique estuary-like systems will be called "riverine coastal wetlands" rather than estuaries because of their several major differences from true marine estuaries (Pritchard 1967). These wetlands most closely fit the Riverine System described by Cowardin et al. (1979), and most of them have areas which would be classified by them as Palustrine Systems.

The riverine coastal wetlands, which here include the freshwater estuary wetlands and parts of the delta wetlands as defined by Herdendorf (1987), differ from other coastal wetland systems of Lake Erie by deriving most of their water from one or more tributaries, with occasional major inputs of lake water via flow reversal. Examples include Old Woman Creek National Estuarine Research Reserve, the lower Maumee River, the lower Sandusky River and Sandusky Bay, and Big Creek Marsh (Fig. 2). Two other types of coastal wetland systems are also recognizable. One, the coastal lagoon wetlands (Herdendorf 1987), includes those marshes which derive their water mostly or entirely from the lake, being separated from it by a sand spit or a barrier beach. Examples are Sheldon Marsh just east of the mouth of Sandusky Bay and Point Pelee National Park, Ontario (Fig. 2). The other type is comprised of marshes which once were an integral part of riverine coastal wetlands but which have been diked and maintain a direct connection to the riverine system only via gates which may be controlled to maintain seasonally desired water levels. Examples of diked marshes include Winous Point Marsh on the northern and southern edges of upper Sandusky Bay, and Moxley Marsh on the southern

shore of the bay (Fig. 2). Each of these three wetland types interacts differently with the lake and undoubtedly is different from the others in terms of its geochemical processes and biological communities. The recent ranges of selected physical and chemical variables are shown for representative marshes, Sandusky Bay and the western basin in Table 2. Herdendorf (1987) has examined our relatively meager understanding of the ecology of the various western Lake Erie wetland systems. This review focuses primarily on the riverine coastal wetlands.

Brant and Herdendorf (1972) determined that nine "estuaries" in the reach from the Maumee River to the Huron River account for 90% of the total estuarine area along the Ohio shore, related primarily "... to the relatively low, flat terrain in northwestern Ohio as opposed to the higher relief of the northeastern section of the state." Their lengths vary greatly from 0.8 km along the lower Rocky River, to 2.1 km along Old Woman Creek, 23.8 km along the Maumee River and 24.8 km along the Sandusky River.

Figure 2. Locations of the Lake Erie coastal marshes cited in this review.

Table 2. Ranges of reported values of physical and chemical parameters from studies of western Lake Erie, Sandusky Bay, and selected marshes.

Parameter	Old Woman Creek Estuary ^{abc}	Sandusky Bay ^d	Lake Erie western basin ^{de}	Moxley Marsh ^f	Winous Point ^f
temperature, °C	0-31	12-29	12-25 (17.3)	13-25	14-32
turbidity	5-310 NTU			20-160 JTU	90-670JTU
total suspended solids, mg/L	27-576	8-975	<1-35 (19.9)		
Secchi depth, m	0.02-0.56	0-0.8	0.4-1.6 (0.80)		
spec. conductance µmhos/cm @ 25°C	176-715	232-644	217-368 (282)		
pH	7.4-8.8	7.0-9.5	7.0-8.8 (8.4)	7.2-7.7	7.4-8.3
dissolved O ₂ , mg/L	0.0-14.4	5.2-19.4	5.6-12.8 (9.8)		
total P, µg/L	60-600	40-500	20-80 (79)		
soluble reactive P, µg/L	<1-283	<1-70	<1-19	50-1,580	200-2,750
nitrate+nitrite N, µg/L	0-13.8	0.0-10.9	0.0-2.0 (0.3)	0.1-12	0.5-14
dissolved reactive silica, mg/L	0.01-11.7	0.02-9.9	0.1-1.1	7-15	5-13
chloride, mg/L	2.2-87.3	12.8-38.3	12.5-23.9	38-75	28-50
total iron, mg/L	0.6-33.6	0.2-14.0	0.1-1.1		
chlorophyll a (corrected) µg/L	-0.8-231	0-110	0-20 (13.5)		
atrazine, µg/L	ND-57 ^g				
alachlor, µg/L	ND-45 ^g				
carbofuran, µg/L	ND-8 ^g				

^a Krieger 1984

^b Heath 1987

^c Klarer 1988

^d Unpubl. data for 1982 and 1983 from Richards and Baker (1985)

^e Values in parentheses are means for 1967-1982 data; Herdendorf 1987

^f Millie 1979 (3 dates except 6 dates for temperature; nitrate without nitrite; Hach kit data)

^g Krieger (unpublished data)

The riverine coastal wetlands display a persistent chemical gradient (measured in parts per million rather than in parts per thousand as in marine estuaries). This gradient is the reverse of that in most true estuaries in that the highest concentrations are upstream, indicating a progressive dilution of tributary water with lake water in a downstream direction. During studies performed in the 1960s, specific conductance in the lower Cuyahoga River showed a nearly fourfold decrease from upstream to downstream, and the colder, less mineralized lake water intruded in some circumstances under the warmer, highly mineralized river water, the extent of intrusion being influenced by seiches, wind and changes in streamflow and lake level (Brant and Herdendorf 1972). In the 14-km (8.5-mile) long Sandusky Bay, which receives water from a 4,600 km² (1,770 sq. mi.) watershed, continuous recordings of specific conductance made on several dates while traversing its long axis revealed regions of "relatively constant" specific conductance separated by "relatively abrupt" transition zones, rather than a long, smooth gradient. The regions were interpreted to be "low flow river water and resident estuary water" (600-1,000 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$), upper bay water (400-700 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$), storm runoff water (200-400 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$), and lake water (around 250 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$) (Richards and Baker 1985).

A progressive decrease in specific conductance in a downstream direction has also been consistently measured in the much smaller Old Woman Creek Wetland (Krieger 1984, Heath 1987, Klarer 1988). Samples collected at 8-hr intervals for several weeks in 1987 near the mouth of the Old Woman Creek Wetland, draining a 69 km² watershed, revealed frequent dramatic oscillations in specific conductance which resulted from the alternate movements of lake water and marsh water past the sampling point (Fig. 3). In that ongoing study, from one to three samples are being collected at both ends of this wetland three times a day year-around and at least one sample per day is being analyzed for nutrients, suspended sediment and specific conductance (also pesticides at varying intervals) in order to measure quantitatively the exchange of water and materials between the lake and wetland and the transformation, trapping and release of materials by the wetland (Krieger and Baker 1988).

In a study of the movement of nutrients through the Old Woman Creek Wetland from March to October 1983, the first storm after spring planting produced the highest nutrient concentrations recorded during the study. During late spring and again after the first storm, the concentrations of soluble reactive phosphorus and nitrite+nitrate declined to undetectable levels (<0.1 and 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$, respectively), whereas dissolved silica stabilized after the first storm near 1 mg/L. All of the nutrient concentrations increased in the marsh upstream but not downstream in response to the later storms (Krieger 1984).

Similarly, the water chemistry of Old Woman Creek Wetland was studied before, during and after three storms in April and October 1984 and May 1985 (Klarer 1988). Three patterns of chemical changes in the storm water were noted over time, as shown in Fig. 4. Turbidity was employed as a marker for storm water from the tributary. (1) It was apparent that calcium (Fig. 4),

magnesium, pH, total alkalinity, sodium, specific conductance, sulfate and chloride were diluted by storm runoff water. (2) However, soluble reactive phosphorus (Fig. 4), iron, copper, zinc, potassium and ammonia, because they were strongly correlated with turbidity, were considered to be associated with the sediment fraction of storm runoff. (3) Dissolved silica, nitrate (Fig. 4) and nitrite increased following the turbidity peak of storm events and were thus considered to be associated with increased interflow (groundwater and drainage tile flow) resulting from the storm (Klarer 1988).

In the Sandusky Bay system, a factor analysis performed on the physical and chemical data for five storms from 1981 through 1983 resolved four groups of highly correlated parameters: (1) phosphorus forms, nitrite+nitrate, dissolved reactive silica, iron, and Secchi depth (negative); (2) suspended solids and turbidity, and usually distance from river mouth (negative); (3) chloride and specific conductance, and usually chlorophyll *a*; (4) dissolved oxygen, oxygen saturation, and pH. The first two groups were combined in all but the first and by far the biggest storm, and the parameters (except Secchi depth and distance) increased in association with storm water (Fig. 5). Groups 3 and 4 were sometimes combined, and the parameters usually were lower in storm water as compared to resident bay water (Fig. 5) (Richards and Baker 1985).

Figure 3. Oscillations in specific conductance (measured at 25°C) about 100 m upstream of the mouth of Old Woman Creek Wetland, revealing the frequent alternation of lake and marsh water masses in that region of the marsh (Krieger, unpubl.).

Figure 4. Temporal and spatial concentration patterns of turbidity, calcium, orthophosphate and nitrate following a May 1985 storm in the Old Woman Creek Wetland (modified from Klarer 1988). Site A is at the creek above the wetland, sites B-H are progressively downstream in the wetland, and site I is in the wave zone of Lake Erie about 100 m west of the wetland mouth.

SOLUBLE REACTIVE PHOSPHORUS SEPTEMBER 1981

CHLOROPHYLL A SEPTEMBER 1981

Figure 5. Concentration gradients in Sandusky Bay for soluble reactive phosphorus and chlorophyll a following a typical storm in September 1981 (modified from Richards and Baker 1985).

The spatial and temporal scales of the storm events in the two systems studied (Richard and Baker 1985, Klarer 1988) were near opposite extremes for Lake Erie riverine coastal systems but nevertheless those parameters which were included in both studies indicated the operation of similar processes. As might be expected the individual chemical parameters show essentially the same kinds of temporal patterns in the riverine coastal wetlands as they do in the upstream tributaries, but their concentration ranges are often narrower because of dilution of the river water by resident marsh water.

Dissolved oxygen concentrations, which can become limiting to freshwater fauna, vary widely over time and space in the few Lake Erie coastal wetlands studied (Table 2). The Old Woman Creek Wetland in the mid-1980's, when the lake was at record high levels, had mostly open water (without macrophytes) and a depth not exceeding 1.5 m except for a few locations in the stream channel where depths approached 2.5 m. One study undertaken during that period showed that dissolved oxygen declined to values below 4 mg/L on some occasions from mid-June into August in parts of the marsh, particularly in the deeper areas, when stream flow was near an annual low (Krieger 1984). A later study showed oxygen levels below 5 mg/L in October and as low as 3 mg/L in May in the same deep areas as the former study, while most of the open water areas had concentrations much higher than 5 mg/L (Klarer 1988). Heath (1987) found that during the summer, oxygen concentration was lower at a mid-marsh location than at either the inlet or outlet of the wetland, despite expectations based on increased productivity of the marsh community at that location. He noted, however, that because oxygen was measured early in the morning, the lower concentrations there may have been the result of greater nighttime respiration within the marsh community. He recorded maximum readings of 12.4-14.4 mg O₂/L at the three locations in December or April, and minimum readings of 0.0, 0.2 and 3.8 mg O₂/L between July and September. The mean values for 14 readings, 10 of which were between June and September, were 6.7-7.7 mg O₂/L, the lowest average being in the mid-marsh channel (Heath 1987). Oxygen values recorded in Big Creek Marsh, adjacent to Long Point Bay, were always above 5 mg/L when sampled in midafternoon monthly from April to November (Mudroch 1981).

Sandusky Bay (with a mean depth in the mid-1980s of about 2.6 m) had a mean dissolved oxygen concentration in 1972 and 1973 of 10.8 mg/L at the surface and 9.8 mg/L at the bottom, with a mean Secchi disk transparency of 4 cm (Lindsay 1976). In the early 1980s the mean saturation level of oxygen in the bay was 99.1%, compared with 91.7% near the surface of Lake Erie and 76.8% in storm water samples taken in the bay and lake (Richards and Baker 1985). These high mean oxygen concentrations in the bay and nearshore area of the lake are in part due to the ability of wind frequently to mix the water completely from top to bottom because of the great surface to depth ratio. The lower oxygen levels noted in the leading portion of storm water in both Sandusky Bay and Old Woman Creek Wetland (Richards and Baker 1985, Klarer 1988) were attributed to reduced algal productivity in the storm water

(i.e., few algae present compared to the resident marsh or bay water) or perhaps increased biochemical oxygen demand (Klarer 1988).

Pesticide occurrences and concentrations in Lake Erie riverine coastal wetlands follow the same seasonal patterns as in the tributaries. In a study of pesticides in Old Woman Creek Wetland from March to October 1983, as noted above in Lake Erie tributaries, the first storm after spring planting (that year in June) produced the highest concentrations of herbicides throughout the marsh that were measured during the study. In part the high concentrations resulted because the large volume of the storm water replaced the resident water in the marsh, and also because the volumes of three other storms in July, August and October were so small that in those cases the storm water was trapped in the upper reaches of the wetland and did not flush it. In the same study, the five herbicides alachlor (Lasso™), atrazine (AAtrex™), linuron (Lorox™), metolachlor (Dual™) and metribuzin (Sencor™, Lexone™) attained a combined concentration of 28 µg/L (ppb), of which atrazine accounted for 11 µg/L. Atrazine and metolachlor persisted at detectable levels for the duration of the study (Krieger 1984).

A later study conducted over three years (1985-1987) showed peak concentrations of atrazine and alachlor, as well as other herbicides over five times higher than in 1983, the result of differences in storm timing, intensity and duration from year to year. The study also showed in both a lower Sandusky River marsh and Old Woman Creek Wetland that peak herbicide concentrations are very similar from the stream channel to the edge of the marsh several hundred meters away, indicating that the storm water and resident marsh water become thoroughly mixed transversely (Fig. 6). Thus, the highest concentrations are not restricted to tributary channels, and the extensive beds of emergent aquatic plants toward the marsh edges are exposed during their growing season to the highest herbicide concentrations (Krieger 1986, Krieger unpubl.).

Only recently have attempts been made to understand the functional role of Great Lakes coastal wetlands in processing sediments, nutrients and other pollutants entering them from their watersheds. Klarer (1988) estimated the role of Old Woman Creek Wetland in reducing the amounts of various chemicals delivered from the creek to the lake by computing output/input ratios from the average concentration values for each storm. The comparison was performed while acknowledging three assumptions which did not always apply: (1) that all of the storm water moved through the wetland and into Lake Erie, (2) that the storm water mass was equally sampled at all sites, and (3) that all flow through the wetland was unidirectional. Corrected to 100% chloride concentration to account for dilution of storm water in the marsh, the ratios indicated a reduction between input and output of 32%-53% of soluble reactive phosphorus entering in storms, 46%-71% of nitrate, and 44% to 54% of silicate. Some of these nutrients potentially were converted to other forms which may have then moved unmeasured into the lake.

Figure 6. Changes in the concentrations of atrazine from April to September 1985 at four stations along a transect in Old Woman Creek Wetland (W1-W4) and a lower Sandusky River marsh (S1-S4). Stations W1 and S1 were in the stream channel; W4 and S4 were about 10 m from shore (Krieger 1986).

Richards and Baker (1985) estimated pollutant loadings from storms at several progressively downstream locations in Sandusky Bay. For a major (25-year recurrence) storm in June 1981, they estimated that the load of total suspended solids declined 46% between a continuously monitored discharge site on the lower Sandusky River (above lake level) and the head of Sandusky Bay. Most of the river below the discharge site is at lake level and is bordered by a narrow band of marshes and wetlands which might serve to dilute the storm water and trap or process some proportion of the pollutants. They estimated that in this river segment the total phosphorus load increased by 2%, soluble reactive phosphorus declined 43% and nitrate+nitrite declined 29%. Their calculations took into account a 42% increase in the watershed area below the monitored site, but the calculations for the bay did not account for frequent flow reversals noted at mid-bay (pers. observ.). Between the head and the middle constriction of the bay (Fig. 2), they calculated the loss of a further 38% of the original total suspended solids load as well as 74% of the total phosphorus load, 22% of soluble reactive phosphorus, and a gain of 8% in the nitrate+nitrite load. At the mouth of the bay, the original storm load as measured in the river was left with only 3% of the suspended solids, 14% of the total phosphorus, 23% of the soluble reactive phosphorus and 49% of the nitrate+nitrite, by their calculations.

The other four storms studied, all much smaller than the first, showed loads at the bay mouth which were only 1%-10% of the river load for suspended solids, 7%-24% for total phosphorus, 4%-10% for soluble reactive phosphorus, and 2%-31% for nitrate+nitrite. The decrease in loading from the river mouth to the lake was at least partly a function of storm water volume and the difference between the storm water and bay water concentrations (Richards and Baker 1985). Although the load reduction calculations were admittedly crude estimates, they served to show the effectiveness of the bay in trapping the materials transported into it via storm water.

Lake Erie riverine coastal wetlands probably serve as net sinks for sediments. Buchanan (1982) estimated from core samples that the sedimentation rate in Old Woman Creek Wetland was 0.76 mm per year prior to agricultural development at the beginning of the nineteenth century, and that the rate has increased by 13 times to about 10 mm per year at present.

Heath (1987) was the first to investigate the mechanisms of transformation of phosphorus forms in a Lake Erie riverine wetland and the transfer of phosphorus between the particulate and dissolved phases to the bacterioplankton and phytoplankton. He concluded that in Old Woman Creek Wetland, phytoplankton growth was not limited by phosphorus availability, on the basis of nutrient addition bioassays, but was probably nitrogen limited, at least in mid-summer. Furthermore, the phosphate turnover time was usually more than 20 minutes, whereas in phosphorus-limited communities it is often less than 5 minutes. He also noted that the particulate N:P ratio was less than 10 in the wetland rather than near 20 or greater as it is in phosphorus-limited systems. Whereas in phosphorus-limited communities soluble reactive

phosphorus (SRP) often reaches undetectable levels ($<1 \mu\text{g/L}$), Heath (1987) found that SRP in Old Woman Creek Wetland rarely fell below $5 \mu\text{g/L}$. This contrasts with the findings of Krieger (1984), who one year earlier had found SRP near detection limits in the wetland for most of June and occasionally in October. Klarer (1988), who sampled the same year as Heath (1987), reported that SRP was below $5 \mu\text{g/L}$ in the more downstream parts of the same wetland following an October storm whose runoff waters did not penetrate the downstream areas. Table 2 indicates that SRP in tributary systems of widely differing sizes falls below $1 \mu\text{g/L}$ and that its maximum values, and those of several other substances, are progressively less as size increases from small wetlands to large embayments to western Lake Erie. Confirmation of this apparent relationship by future values obtained from other riverine coastal wetlands would be suggestive of a progressively greater capacity to assimilate these substances in systems of increasing size, perhaps primarily through greater dilution. Nitrate shows the same relationship with size of system as SRP and total P, but the detection limit for nitrate is typically 100 times higher than for SRP. Thus, the data currently available do not permit a comparison of the lower limits of SRP and nitrate.

Based on changes noted in the distribution and metabolism of phosphorus components between upstream and downstream regions of the wetland, Heath (1987) concluded that it "greatly ameliorated" the availability of phosphorus to Lake Erie phytoplankton. The reduced availability of phosphorus was accomplished by increasing the proportions of particulate and soluble forms of phosphorus from which phosphate was only slowly released if at all. He showed that the sediments act as both a phosphorus sink (under aerobic conditions) and as a phosphorus source (under anaerobic conditions). Uptake by the sediments was shown to involve both ion-exchange sorption to surfaces and uptake by biota associated with the sediments (Heath 1987).

Mudroch (1981) assumed a complete mixing of discharged and receiving water and calculated that a complete discharge of the 850-ha Big Creek Marsh into Long Point Bay would increase the organic nitrogen concentration by 0.004 mg/L (ppm) and the total phosphorus concentration by $<0.001 \text{ mg/L}$. This would amount to 0.017 g of total nitrogen/ m^2/yr and 0.0008 g of total phosphorus/ m^2/yr exported to the bay. It is unlikely, however, that these discharges occur because, as Mudroch (1981) noted, Big Creek courses along the northern border of the marsh, which has no other outlet to the bay. Thus, it is likely that most Big Creek water flows directly past the marsh and into the lake, and in the likely absence of frequent seiches or storm surges which would empty and refill the marsh, much of the marsh water probably has a residence time measurable in months rather than the 4 days assumed by Mudroch (1981). Nevertheless, as she concluded, "it is obvious that the marshes contribute very little to the nutrient loading of [Lake] Erie" (Mudroch 1981, p. 33).

Within six lower Great Lakes marshes in Canada, including Big Creek Marsh, Mudroch (1981) noted a high positive correlation between the annual loading of total N and the above-ground biomass production of *Typha latifolia* (cattail). Most of the N present in the marsh water was organic N. "All of the

marshes showed a high capacity to retain nutrients and metals" (Mudroch 1981, p. 40).

Coastal marsh sediments and their chemistry probably strongly influence the marsh water chemistry. This is partly because the surface sediments in these very shallow systems are easily resuspended into the water column by wind, particularly where no emergent or floating-leaved macrophytes are present to prevent or dampen waves. Sediment resuspension permits sediment pore water, which is often anoxic (without oxygen) and contains various reduced chemical constituents, to mix with the oxygenated water column. Furthermore, fresh sediments entering the wetland serve as the vehicle for many pollutants (e.g., phosphorus, heavy metals and various persistent organics such as pesticides) adsorbed to the sediment surfaces.

The annual suspended sediment (total suspended solids) load for the Sandusky River above lake level was shown in Fig. 1. These values include the sediment resuspension from the bed surface of the finer silts and clays with the onset of rising storm flow (Baker 1988) but do not take into account the saltational, sliding or rolling downstream migration of bedload materials (Leopold et al. 1964) during freshets, which is believed to be a negligible proportion of the total sediment loading to the lake.

Frizado et al. (1986) examined the mineralogy of Old Woman Creek Wetland sediments and concluded that they most probably derived from glacial till, glacial lacustrine sediments, and soils. Because of differential transport and deposition of the source components, the surface deposit in the wetland contains fewer carbonate minerals, fewer clay minerals, and more quartz than the original source material. "After burial of the estuarine sediments, the post-burial or diagenetic processes become operative. The concentrations of most trace elements are higher in the interstitial waters than in the overlying water. Therefore, the sediments will act as a source of trace elements to the estuarine waters" (Frizado et al. 1986). These workers stopped short of measuring the actual contribution of trace elements from the sediments. They did measure several heavy metals in the sediments, which had a pH ranging from 7.0-8.7 with a maximum value within the upper 10 cm of sediment. Iron and manganese were the most abundant of the elements they analyzed in interstitial water, usually above 200 ppb. Cadmium, chromium and lead were usually below 15 ppb, cobalt usually below 30 ppb, copper below 50 ppb and nickel usually below 74 ppb. The interstitial concentrations of sodium, potassium, magnesium and calcium were very similar to the average concentration of the overlying surface water.

Big Creek Marsh was found to have "no large differences" in concentrations of magnesium, calcium, sodium, potassium, manganese and phosphorus in surface sediments except for high concentrations of calcium in an area covered by a dense growth of *Elodea*. It was surmised that the calcium may have come from calcium carbonate precipitation on the plants (Mudroch 1981). The pH in Big Creek Marsh sediments fell in a narrow range, between 6.9 and 7.0. Surface sediment concentrations of lead, copper, nickel, chromium and zinc

were lower than those in the surficial sediments of Lake Erie, but elevated concentrations of arsenic and mercury were found in the part of the marsh most affected by inflow from Big Creek, which Mudroch (1981) associated with agricultural residues.

Heavy metals have been detected in the water column by the analysis of unfiltered water samples. Richards and Baker (1985) cited evidence that total iron in Sandusky Bay storm water is strongly sediment bound, but they also found evidence of a dissolved component. Copper was less strongly associated with storm runoff than iron, and it appeared to be entering the bay primarily in the spring. Other metals were rarely detected. In Old Woman Creek Wetland, Klarer (1988) noted that the concentrations of iron, copper, zinc and manganese increased at the onset of storm runoff events and then quickly declined. All of these metals appeared to be strongly associated with suspended sediment inputs as measured by turbidity.

LAKE ERIE

It is far beyond the scope of this review to address adequately the chemical limnology and contaminants of the harbors and open waters of Lake Erie. Excellent books (Rousmaniere 1979, Burns 1985) and extensive government reports (e.g., Internat. Joint Commis. 1980; Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985, 1987; Herdendorf 1984; Lesht and Rockwell 1987) have been written which bring together an exhaustive body of scientific evidence to explain the nature and extent of the problems brought about by the nutrient enrichment of the lake from point and nonpoint sources, and by the presence of persistent toxic substances from primarily point sources. The fate, distribution and biological effects of many of the hundreds of organic chemicals now residing in the sediments or water of Lake Erie (refer to the overview in this volume by Herdendorf and Krieger) are poorly understood or are unknown, both from the standpoint of individual compounds and combinations of interacting compounds.

The problems of nutrient and toxic chemical contamination of the lake have long histories, and remedial programs were developed on a large scale in both Canada and the U.S.A. only in the late 1960s and 1970s. Progress in reducing the severity of contamination has, for most substances, been accomplished; but only through legislation and enforcement, as well as through continued scientific investigation into the sources and results of contamination, can this progress be continued and expanded. Recent trends for only two of the many problems -- annual oxygen depletion in the central basin, and persistent toxics in sediments and fish -- are briefly summarized here.

Late summer oxygen depletion to the point of anoxia in the central basin was first documented in the late 1920s and progressively became more extensive and more prolonged over the next four decades as phosphorus inputs to the lake continued unabated. Excessive bioavailable phosphorus, from the sources described earlier, permitted increasingly greater production of

algae in the open lake (the phytoplankton) and along shore (see Monaco and Lorenz, this volume), accompanied by changes in algal species, filter clogging and taste and odor problems in water supplies, and increased turbidity. The increase in phytoplankton production, which can be measured chemically as chlorophyll *a* concentration (e.g., Fig. 5), permitted a large increase in the production of the zooplankton as well as a change in its composition (see Klarer, this volume), which in turn provided more food for the fish and other animals which feed on the zooplankton. The increase in algal production further led to visible "blooms" of algae from spring on into the fall each year. Mats of algae washed onto beaches in large quantities, presenting aesthetic and odor problems.

The annual spring bloom of algae was followed by a "crash" or sudden decline in the amount of algae in the lake as their nutrients (especially silica, phosphorus and nitrogen) were used up. The algal crash led to a similar crash of the zooplankton. This annual bloom-and-crash cycle provided large amounts of organic matter which settled to the lake bottom. Thus, with the continued increase in phosphorus inputs over the decades, the annual deposition of organic debris on the lake bottom increased. As these materials were decomposed by respiring microorganisms, the demand for dissolved oxygen during the summer in the lower depths of the lake increased as well. It is during the same season that thermal stratification of the lake takes place. This stratification prevents the surface water layer (the epilimnion), rich in dissolved oxygen, from mixing with and replenishing the oxygen in the layer of deeper and dark waters of the lower depths (the hypolimnion).

Once the summer stratification begins, the oxygen in the hypolimnion cannot be replenished until the fall overturn destroys the thermal structure and mixes the upper and lower water masses. For at least the past half century, all of the oxygen in part of the shallow hypolimnion of the central basin (variable from 2.7 m to 7.7 m thick, June-August; Lesht and Rockwell 1987) has been consumed by respiratory demand, leaving an anoxic area of greater or lesser extent (Fig. 7). The seasonal oxygen depletion has had a profound effect on the fish and invertebrate community structures of the central basin (see the reviews by Johnson and Klarer, this volume). Severe oxygen depletion rarely occurs in the shallow western basin because wind action in most years prevents hypolimnion development, but anoxia in that basin has been reported to have had devastating effects on the biota (Britt 1955). Anoxia has not been recorded in the open waters of the deep eastern basin, which is the least productive of the three basins and whose thick hypolimnion contains sufficient volume to meet the demands for oxygen.

Although phosphorus loading reductions to the lake have been achieved, the goal of restoring aerobic conditions in the hypolimnion of the central basin has been elusive. "Despite the documented decreases in point source phosphorus loadings to Lake Erie, oxygen depletion rates continued to increase through the 1970s and have now stabilized, fluctuating between 3.2 and 3.7 mg/L per month" (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987, p. 86). In 1985 the stratified period was longer than normal, with an anoxic hypolimnion

Figure 7. Areal extent of summer anoxia in the hypolimnion of the central basin of Lake Erie (Herdendorf 1984).

from late August through mid-September and a depletion rate of 3.7 mg/L per month (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987).

Phosphorus concentrations in the open waters of Lake Erie vary widely and have not decreased in the same proportion as the load reductions, partly because bioavailable phosphorus is released from sediments via regeneration in anoxic sediments and subsequent wave resuspension. However, evidence of slowly declining phosphorus concentrations is manifested by the large reduction in basin-wide blooms of planktonic blue-green algae in western Lake Erie as well as in reduced massive growths of attached green algae (*Cladophora*) between the mid-1960s and the present. Basin-wide blooms have been absent in recent years, and the open lake phytoplankton has decreased in abundance and reverted to a more mesotrophic species composition (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985).

On the basis of Secchi depth and the average total or particulate phosphorus and chlorophyll *a* concentrations in the surface waters, the trophic status has been determined for different regions of Lake Erie (Fig. 8). Most of the western basin and Sandusky Bay, Presque Isle Bay, and the southern nearshore zone of most of the central basin are classified as eutrophic, while most of the rest of the lake is considered mesotrophic. An area in the middle of the lake straddling the central and eastern basins is oligo/mesotrophic. The trophic regions shown in Fig. 8 are general and vary according to the exact classification scheme used. A discussion of the effects on classification of the seasonally dynamic variables used, and of the differences among the several indices that have been used, is found in Lesht and Rockwell (1987).

Baumann and Whittle (1988) have placed the problem of selected persistent organic contaminants in Lake Erie into perspective with the other Great Lakes in their recent compilation and interpretation of evidence collected by both the U.S. and Canadian governments. Analyses of whole-fish tissues from Lake Erie show a gradual decline between 1979 and 1985 in body burdens of DDT (dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane), whose use was banned in both countries in 1970-1972 (Fig. 9). DDT may be approaching an equilibrium level which "... may be maintained primarily by inputs from sediment sinks and from airborne deposition" (Baumann and Whittle 1988).

Fish from Lake Erie have also shown a gradual decline in PCB levels since 1979 (Fig. 9). Much of the present input of PCBs to the lake is from atmospheric deposition (Baumann and Whittle 1988). Fig. 10 shows the lakewide distribution of PCBs in surface sediments in the early 1970s. In the 1980s the highest PCB concentrations are in the western basin and coincide with inputs from the Detroit River (Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1987).

PAHs (polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons) are produced from incomplete combustion of organic matter and by a number of industrial processes. Two PAHs, fluoranthene and benzo(*a*)pyrene (B(*a*)P), are found in especially high concentrations in the sediments of the lower Black River, Cleveland Harbor, the Buffalo River and eastern Lake Erie and have been linked to carcinogenicity in

Figure 8. Trophic status of regions of Lake Erie (Herdendorf, unpubl.)

Figure 9. Trends for whole-fish tissue burdens of DDT and PCBs in Lake Erie (modified from Baumann and Whittle 1988).

Figure 10. PCB concentrations (ppb= $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) in surface sediments of lakes Erie and St. Clair and the southernmost parts of lakes Huron and Ontario in the early 1970s (PLUARG 1978).

fish. At all three of these locations where fish studies have been conducted, high frequencies of various kinds of tumors have been found in resident fish, especially bottom feeding species. Whole brown bullhead from the Black River, 84% of whose population had "either early tissue changes in the neoplastic process or more advanced lesions", contained over 1 ppm of fluoranthene and over 5 ppb of B(a)P (Baumann and Whittle 1988).

In summary, the pollution of Lake Erie has resulted gradually over many decades from intentional abuses as well as from an ignorance of the ecological processes operating in the lake basin. Only by determining and understanding the continuing nonpoint and point source pollution problems in the individual watersheds, the role of the coastal wetlands in ameliorating pollutants, and the ultimate response of the lake itself to various kinds of pollution, can we hope to restore the water and sediment quality of Lake Erie. Progress is being made, but many research and management needs remain. Many of the needs have been detailed in the annual reports of the International Joint Commission (e.g., PLUARG 1978, Internat. Joint Commission 1980, Great Lakes Water Quality Board 1985, 1987). The remaining Lake Erie coastal wetlands may play an important role in trapping, processing and releasing nutrients and other contaminants to the lake. This role needs to be measured quantitatively in order to understand their value as buffer zones between the tributaries and the lake. Furthermore, the transformational processes in the wetlands which are thought to be important in reducing the bioavailability of nutrients or the toxicity of persistent industrial organics to the lake biota need to be deciphered and quantified.

REFERENCES

- Baker, D.B. 1988. Sediment, nutrient and pesticide transport in selected lower Great Lakes tributaries. U.S. Environ. Protection Agency, Chicago, Illinois. EPA 905/4-88-001. 117 pp. + app.
- Baker, D.B., K.A. Krieger, R.P. Richards and J.W. Kramer. 1985. Effects of intensive agricultural land use on regional water quality in northwestern Ohio. pp. 201-207. *In: Perspectives on nonpoint source pollution. Proc. National Conf. May 19-22, Kansas City, Missouri.* U.S. Environ. Protection Agency, Washington, D.C. EPA 440/5-85-001.
- Baker, D.B., K.A. Krieger, and J.V. Setzler. 1981. The concentrations and transport of pesticides in northwestern Ohio rivers - 1981. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Buffalo, New York. Tech. Rept. Series No. 20. 33 pp. + app.
- Baumann, P.C., and D.M. Whittle. 1988. The status of selected organics in the Laurentian Great Lakes: an overview of DDT, PCBs, dioxins, furans, and aromatic hydrocarbons. *Aquatic Toxicology* 11: 241-257.

- Blake, G.A. 1988. The effects of the agricultural herbicide alachlor on total biomass and community structure of algal periphyton in artificial streams. M.S. thesis. Bowling Green State Univ., Bowling Green, Ohio. 77 pp.
- Brant, R.A., and C.E. Herdendorf. 1972. Delineation of Great Lakes estuaries. Proc. 15th Conf. Great Lakes Res. 1972: 710-718. Internat. Assoc. Great Lakes Res.
- Britt, N.W. 1955. Stratification in western Lake Erie in summer of 1953: effects on the Hexagenia (Ephemeroptera) population. *Ecology* 36: 239-244.
- Buchanan, D.B. 1982. Transport and deposition of sediment in Old Woman Creek Estuary, Erie County, Ohio. M.S. Thesis. Ohio State Univ., Columbus, Ohio. 198 pp.
- Burns, N.M. 1985. Erie, the lake that survived. Rowman & Allanheld Publ., Totowa, New Jersey. 320 pp.
- Cowardin, L.M., V. Carter, F.C. Golet, and E.T. LaRoe. 1979. Classification of wetlands and deepwater habitats of the United States. U.S. Dept. Interior, Fish and Wildlife Serv., Washington, D.C. FWS/OBS-79/31. 131 pp.
- Frizado, J., R. Anderhalt, C. Mancuso, and L. Norman. 1986. Depositional and diagenetic processes in a freshwater estuary. U.S. Dept. Commerce, NOAA, Office of Ocean and Coastal Resource Mgt., Washington, D.C. 226 pp.
- Great Lakes Phosphorus Task Force. 1985. United States task force plan for phosphorus load reductions from non-point, and point sources on Lake Erie, Lake Ontario, and Saginaw Bay. U.S. Environ. Protection Agency, Chicago, Illinois.
- Great Lakes Water Quality Board. 1985. 1985 report on Great Lakes water quality. Internat. Joint Commis., Windsor, Ontario. 212 pp.
- Great Lakes Water Quality Board. 1987. 1987 report on Great Lakes water quality. Internat. Joint Commis., Windsor, Ontario. 236 pp.
- Heath, R.T. 1987. Phosphorus dynamics in the Old Woman Creek National Estuarine Research Reserve--a preliminary investigation. NOAA Tech. Memorandum NOS MEMD 11. U.S. Dept. Commerce, Washington, D.C. 105 pp.
- Herdendorf, C.E. 1984. Lake Erie water quality 1970-1982: a management assessment. U.S. Environ. Protection Agency, Chicago, Illinois. EPA-905/4-84-007. 144 pp.
- Herdendorf, C.E. 1987. The ecology of the coastal marshes of western Lake Erie: a community profile. U.S. Dept. Interior, Fish and Wildlife Serv., Washington, D.C. Biol. Rep. 85(7.9). 171 pp.

- Honey Creek Joint Bd. Supervisors. 1982. Honey Creek watershed project, final program evaluation report, 1979-1981. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Buffalo, New York. 57 pp.
- Internat. Joint Commission. 1980. Pollution in the Great Lakes Basin from land use activities. Windsor, Ontario. 141 pp.
- Klarer, D.M. 1988. The role of a freshwater estuary in mitigating stormwater inflow. Ohio Dept. Natural Resources, Columbus, Ohio. 54 pp.
- Krieger, K.A. 1984. Transport and assimilation of nutrients and pesticides in a Lake Erie estuary. U.S. Dept. Commerce, NOAA, U.S. Office of Ocean and Coastal Resource Mgt., Washington, D.C. 46 pp. + app.
- Krieger, K.A. 1986. Exposure of Lake Erie wetlands to agricultural pesticides in storm runoff. pp. 265-289. *In*: Ohio Sea Grant Program proposal 1986-1987, Vol. 2. Ohio State Univ., Columbus, Ohio.
- Krieger, K.A., and D.B. Baker. 1988. An ecosystem approach to Lake Erie coastal wetlands: sediment, nutrient and pesticide budgets. Continuation proposal. pp. 217-235. *In*: Ohio Sea Grant Program 1988-1990 proposal, Vol. 2. Ohio State Univ., Columbus, Ohio.
- Krieger, K.A., D.B. Baker, and J.W. Kramer. 1988. Effects of herbicides on stream *Aufwuchs* productivity and nutrient uptake. *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 17: 299-306.
- Leopold, L.B., M.G. Wilman, and J.P. Miller. 1964. Fluvial processes in geomorphology. W.H. Freeman & Co., San Francisco. 522 pp.
- Lesht, B.M., and D.C. Rockwell. 1987. The state of the middle Great Lakes: results of the 1984 water quality survey of lakes Erie, Huron, and Michigan. ANL/ER-87-1. Argonne Nat. Lab., Argonne, Illinois. 141 pp. + app.
- Lindsay, W.K. 1976. Sandusky Bay, Ohio as a distinct freshwater estuary. Ph.D. Diss., The Ohio State Univ., Columbus, Ohio. 290 pp.
- Millie, D.F. 1979. The epiphytic diatom flora of three species of aquatic vascular plants common to three Lake Erie marshes. M.S. Thesis. Bowling Green State Univ., Bowling Green, Ohio. 205 pp.
- Mudroch, A. 1981. A study of selected Great Lakes coastal marshes. Scientific Series No. 122. National Water Res. Inst., Inland Waters Dir., Environment Canada, Burlington, Ontario. 44 pp.
- National Assoc. Conserv. Districts. 1985. Lake Erie conservation tillage demonstration projects: evaluating management of pesticides, fertilizer, residue to improve water quality. Fort Wayne, Indiana. 22 pp.

- Ohio Coop. Ext. Serv. 1987. Nitrate in drinking water. Bull. 744, Agdex 750. Ohio State Univ., Columbus, Ohio. 7 pp.
- PLUARG, Internat. Ref. Group on Great Lakes Pollution from Land Use Activities. 1978. Environmental management strategy for the Great Lakes system. Internat. Joint Commis., Windsor, Ontario. 113 pp.
- Pritchard, D.W. 1967. What is an estuary: physical viewpoint. pp. 3-5. *In*: Lauff, G.H. (ed.). Estuaries. Publ. No. 83, A.A.A.S., Washington, D.C.
- Richards, R.P. 1987. Monte Carlo studies of sampling strategies for estimating tributary loads. *Water Resources Res.* 23: 1939-1948.
- Richards, R.P., and D.B. Baker. 1985. Assimilation and flux of sediments and pollutants in the Sandusky River estuary, Sandusky Bay, and the adjacent nearshore zone of Lake Erie. U.S. Dept. Commerce, NOAA, Seattle, Washington. 158 pp.
- Rousmaniere, J. (ed.). 1979. The enduring Great Lakes. W.W. Norton & Co., New York. 112 pp.
- Spain, J.D., D.B. Drown, and J.M. Yanko. 1969. The use of concentrations of electrolytes and naturally fluorescent materials to study water mass movements in a freshwater "estuary". *Proc. 12th Conf. Great Lakes Res.* 1969: 723-733. Internat. Assoc. Great Lakes Res.
- Yaksich, S.M. 1983. Summary report of the Lake Erie Wastewater Management Study. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Buffalo, New York. 31 pp.